

EFFICIENT DATA UTILIZATION IN DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS FOR INFERENCE RELIABILITY

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ABSTRACT

In today’s data-driven world, the exponential growth of data across various sectors presents unique opportunities and challenges. In this paper, we propose a novel method tailored to enhance the efficiency of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) in managing these vast data amounts. The primary challenge addressed is the ability of DNNs to provide inferences on the minimal amount of data without sacrificing their quality, a significant concern given the vast scales involved in big data analytics. Our approach emphasizes DNN inference efficiency and reliability, enabling DNNs to deliver accurate inferences while substantially reducing computational complexity. This study explores the increasingly attractive deployment of DNNs for complex tasks, focusing on determining the minimal amount of data necessary to ensure optimal network performance and reliable inference outputs, improving the applicability of DNNs across various big data environments.

Index Terms— Deep Neural Networks, Big Data, DNN inference

1. INTRODUCTION

The exponential growth of data across various domains presents a formidable challenge for conventional machine learning models, especially Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) that are reliant on extensive datasets for effective training and testing. This surge in data volume is characterized by the continuous generation and storage of large-scale high-dimensional data [1]. The magnitude of this high-dimensional data not only opens up new avenues for data analytics but also introduces complex challenges. Experimental evidence shows that effectively exploiting and managing big datasets can lead to informed decisions and enhanced performance [2]. However, the computations required for DNNs are often highly complex and time-consuming due to the intricate structure and large scale of the datasets [3]. The complexity inherent in its high-dimensional nature can introduce significant noise and lead to the emergence of misleading correlations [4]. Additionally, when the expansive dimensionality is coupled with the substantial data volumes, it

places a heavy burden on computational resources, which can result in unstable algorithmic performance [5]. The diverse and extensive Big Data datasets are often compiled from multiple disparate sources, and collected at various times using a range of technologies. This leads to notable challenges in maintaining consistency across the data, addressing variations and statistical biases [1]. Given these complexities, there is an escalating demand for the development of more advanced and robust analytical methods. These methods must not only handle the scale and diversity of the data effectively but also mitigate the risks of error and inefficiency introduced by the high-dimensional characteristics of Big Data. As such, ensuring the validity of statistical analyses in this context is becoming increasingly imperative, highlighting the need for innovative approaches that can adapt to and overcome the challenges presented by the Big Data landscape.

Recently, DNNs have seen extensive use across a range of computer vision tasks, significantly enhancing their accuracy. These applications include image classification [6], object detection [7], speech recognition [8], and action recognition [9]. Deep learning models, however, often struggle with real-world applications when there is a mismatch between the distributions of training and testing data [10]. Typically, a DNN is trained on a set of labeled data and later applied to new, unlabeled data during the inference phase, with both datasets presumed to share the same label space [11, 12, 13, 14]. Over the years, researchers have contributed to the evolution of DNNs and their inference performance, introducing novel architectures and optimization techniques. The efficiency and accuracy of simple DNN inference have been explored, considering factors such as computational speed ensuring that the model’s deployment is effective [15, 16, 17, 18]. Challenges arise when a DNN encounters data points during inference that are statistical outliers—these data points that the model has never encountered before [19]. Especially handling such scenarios effectively on large datasets demands substantial computational resources and time [20]. The large size and unique composition of these datasets often result in a higher occurrence of outlier data, which complicates their management and analysis. Instead of providing inference across entire datasets to evaluate the model performance on a task, it is more practical to work with a smaller subset of the data

that still can ensure the reliability of the inferences. This approach not only reduces the computational burden but enables more efficient management of resources while maintaining the effectiveness of the model in making reliable inferences.

A key challenge in deploying DNNs, particularly in handling vast amounts of data, is evaluating the model’s familiarity with an entire dataset. Traditional research on machine learning systems typically involves independently testing models on each sample to assess their performance. In classification scenarios, this involves categorizing each sample into a specific class based on predefined scores. Although this method is straightforward, it requires considerable effort and time, particularly with larger datasets, where analyzing each individual data point becomes necessary. A more streamlined approach involves assessing the entire dataset’s familiarity to the DNN without the need to conduct inferences on each sample. This strategy would greatly enhance efficiency in managing large-scale data, facilitating faster and more scalable determinations about the dataset’s relevance without extensive data processing. It’s crucial to establish whether the dataset contains images or data points already known to the DNN or if it includes new, previously unseen instances. Equally important is establishing the minimum amount of data necessary for the DNN to deliver accurate and reliable inferences. This method not only conserves computational resources but also expedites the decision-making process, ensuring that the DNN remains robust and reliable in dynamic, real-world applications.

In this study, we introduce an efficient data utilization strategy in DNNs for enhanced inference reliability. We propose an innovative approach that evaluates the performance of a DNN in handling large datasets without the need to generate inferences for the entire dataset. Our primary goal is to ascertain whether a dataset has been previously encountered by a DNN and, thus, if the DNN can produce reliable and accurate inferences. To achieve this, we aim to determine the optimal data quantity required by DNNs to ensure that their inferences are both accurate and reliable, without the necessity of utilizing the entire dataset. This approach significantly reduces the need for extensive testing across large datasets, thereby decreasing computational complexity typically associated with large-scale data processing. It focuses on assessing how well a DNN has integrated knowledge from its training data and its capability to apply this knowledge effectively to new, unseen data. We advocate that this strategy not only aims to reduce the computational complexity of the DNNs but also ensures that the networks maintain high reliability and accuracy in their predictions, thus addressing some of the key challenges in Big Data analysis.

2. PROPOSED METHOD

This paper emphasizes the need for an effective strategy to manage large datasets when employing DNNs, especially

during the inference stage. In Big data environments, it is critical to establish the minimal amount of test data necessary for DNN classifiers to reliably predict outcomes across an entire dataset without the need to individually analyze each data point. We introduce a novel method for statistically analyzing DNN inferences, aiming at reducing computational complexity while ensuring the reliability of these inferences. Our approach suggests that optimal performance and generation of reliable predictions in Big data environments can be achieved not by processing the entire dataset but by utilizing a sufficient subset of data to guarantee reliability. This strategy also allows us to determine whether the dataset has been previously encountered by the model during its training and whether the model is capable of handling the task. This approach offers a pragmatic and effective solution to the challenges of making DNN-based inferences on extensive datasets in classification tasks.

Fig. 1. Through our experiments, we determine the minimum amount of data required to provide reliable inferences while maintaining high performance. Our method demonstrates that achieving optimal inference accuracy in Big data environments does not require processing the entire dataset; instead, it efficiently delivers reliable inferences using the fewest necessary data points.

To establish the necessary sample size for accurate DNN inferences in the classification problems we explore, individual tests of the DNN are carried out across a range of dataset cardinalities. These range from a single data sample to larger quantities (e.g., up to two thousand data samples, N , in our

simulation experiments). The mean value \bar{e} and the variance σ_e^2 of the evaluation metric values $e_i, i = 1, \dots, N$ for the total samples of testing evaluation values is defined as:

$$\bar{e} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N e_i \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_e^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (e_i - \bar{e})^2 \quad (2)$$

For each one of these cardinalities in the range $[1, \dots, 2000]$, the networks are tested repeatedly multiple times so that the mean value and the variation of the evaluation metric can safely be estimated. The selection of data cardinalities was determined through extensive experimentation, revealing that further expansion of the dataset is unnecessary. In the scenarios examined, where the focus is on image classification, classification accuracy is utilized as the evaluation metric

To verify the normal distribution of the evaluation metrics, essential for applying statistical methods accurately, the Shapiro-Wilk normality test [21] is employed on a random sample of 500 values. The normal distribution of our data adheres to the empirical rule showcasing the characteristics of a normal distribution and its relevance to our statistical analyses. Using the 95% confidence interval, we determined the sufficient number of testing samples needed for reliable DNN inferences. A confidence interval is a statistical range derived from a sample of data that is utilized to estimate a population parameter. The interval is accompanied by a confidence level, representing the degree of confidence in the interval containing the true population parameter. The most commonly used confidence intervals include those with confidence levels of 90%, 95%, and 99% with critical values (Z-scores) of 1.645, 1.96, and 2.576 respectively. Specifically, a 95% confidence interval indicates that if we were to repeatedly sample from a population and calculate a 95% confidence interval for each sample, approximately 95 out of 100 intervals would contain the true mean value (μ). The true mean value (μ) is a population parameter that represents the average value of a variable across the entire population. When aiming to generate a 95% confidence interval estimate for an unknown population mean, it implies that there is a 95% probability that the confidence interval will encompass the true population mean. Thus, $P([\text{sample mean}] - \text{margin of error} < \mu < [\text{sample mean}] + \text{margin of error}) = 0.95$. The 95% confidence interval for the population n mean can be expressed as:

$$95\% \text{ confidence interval} = \bar{X} \pm 1.96\sigma/\sqrt{n}. \quad (3)$$

According to our proposed method, the minimum sample size was established to ensure that, with this quantity of data, the evaluation metric falls within the 95% confidence interval of the overall sample mean. More specifically, to ascertain the sufficient number of testing samples needed, we first confirm

that the evaluation metric values adhere to a Gaussian distribution. This verification allows for the calculation of the sample mean, sample standard deviation and confidence intervals for the population mean. Then, the minimum number of testing samples needed is determined based on the condition that the evaluation metric corresponding to that number equals the total sample size mean value, with a 95% confidence interval. In particular, when using the proposed method, the quantity of testing samples needed corresponds to the number of samples necessary for the network to attain an evaluation metric equivalent to:

$$\bar{e} + 1.96\sigma_e/\sqrt{N}. \quad (4)$$

This criterion ensures a sufficient level of confidence in the DNN’s conclusions while maintaining the high performance of the model.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we present the experimental results of our method applied to various datasets. Our aim is to identify the minimum number of samples required for DNNs to provide reliable inferences. By determining the minimum sample size, we can assess whether the dataset was previously encountered during the model’s training. This approach ensures optimal performance while reducing computational complexity and maintaining the production of reliable predictions in Big data environments.

We present experimental results across various datasets to showcase the benefits of our proposed approach. Experiments were conducted on four well-known image classification datasets: MNIST [22], Fashion MNIST [23], Cifar 10 and 100 [24]. MNIST and Fashion MNIST consist of 60K training and 10K testing grayscale images equally distributed among 10 object classes. Cifar-10 and 100 consist of 50K training and 10K testing grayscale images equally distributed among 10 and 100 object classes respectively.

To ascertain the optimal number of test samples necessary for trustworthy inferences, the DNN is subjected to testing using varying unknown testing sample sizes. In our experiments, the AlexNet [25] DNN architecture is used. AlexNet features eight layers with learnable parameters, comprising five convolutional layers—some of which are followed by max pooling—and three fully connected layers. To assess the performance of the DNN classifier, classification accuracy is employed as the evaluation metric. The primary outcomes of this study are presented in Table 1, which showcases the experimental results across multiple datasets.

Figure 2 depicts the plot illustrating the correlation between the number of samples and the accuracy scores. The plot demonstrates that with an increasing number of samples, the range of classification accuracy scores becomes narrower. It is observed that when testing with limited data, misclassified data significantly affects the model’s evaluation. The

Table 1. Alex-Net Classification Accuracy of Multiple Datasets

Dataset	Number of Testing Samples	Mean Evaluation Metric	Standard Deviation
F-MNIST [23]	15	0.9000	0.0573
	50	0.9392	0.0269
	500	0.9214	0.0113
	1000	0.9249	0.0051
	1500	0.9285	0.0030
	2000	0.9219	0.0057
Cifar-10 [24]	15	0.8667	0.0894
	50	0.8137	0.0735
	500	0.8184	0.0160
	1000	0.8206	0.0119
	1500	0.8178	0.0129
	2000	0.8175	0.0090
Cifar-100 [24]	15	0.5438	0.1282
	50	0.5863	0.0773
	500	0.6122	0.0366
	1000	0.6107	0.0175
	1500	0.6117	0.0072
	2000	0.6167	0.0117
MNIST [22]	15	1.0000	0.0000
	50	0.9960	0.0080
	500	0.9952	0.0034
	1000	0.9956	0.0019
	1500	0.9953	0.0022
	2000	0.9948	0.0014

classification accuracy scores stabilize after a certain number of samples, suggesting that additional increases in sample size do not significantly affect the performance. This stabilization indicates that the model can deliver accurate inferences even with few data points.

Fig. 2. AlexNet classification accuracy scores and the number of samples plot on the F-MNIST dataset [23].

The minimum test data set cardinality needed to ensure reliable and accurate DNN inferences is determined based on the results presented in Table 1. These estimations are ob-

tained using the methodology described in Section 2. The values indicating the minimum sample sizes for various training datasets are presented in Table 2. The outcomes reveal that the DNN model can be deemed reliable when delivering inferences for around 1% of the data it is trained on. This finding indicates that the model can effectively handle large volumes of data while requiring significantly fewer data points to produce reliable inferences.

Table 2. Minimum number of data required to ensure reliable DNN (AlexNet [25]) inferences for each dataset and the percentage in relation to the training dataset size.

Dataset	Samples needed	Percentage of samples needed
F-MNIST [23]	335	0.55%
Cifar-10 [24]	305	0.61%
Cifar-100 [24]	362	0.72%
MNIST [22]	253	0.42%

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we present an innovative strategy for managing large datasets using DNNs to make accurate inferences. We introduce a method that identifies the minimal amount of test data necessary for DNN classifiers to reliably predict outcomes across an entire dataset without requiring individual analysis of each data point. Our strategy advocates that achieving optimal performance and trustworthy predictions in Big data environments does not necessitate processing the entire dataset. Instead, this approach focuses on providing reliable inferences with optimal accuracy using the minimal necessary amount of data points. This approach offers a pragmatic solution to the challenges of conducting DNN-based inferences on large datasets, particularly within the context of classification tasks. Our experimental results confirm that only a small portion of the total dataset is required for DNNs to produce accurate and reliable inferences, thus mitigating the need to handle the vast amounts of data. This efficiency opens new possibilities for DNN inference analysis and sets the stage for further research into optimizing DNN configurations for Big data analysis, extending their practical utility across a variety of settings.

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5. REFERENCES

- [1] J. Fan, F. Han, and H. Liu, "Challenges of big data analysis," *National science review*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 293–314, 2014.
- [2] H. Chiroma, U. A. Abdullahi, A. A. Alarood, L. A. Gabralla, N. Rana, L. Shuib, I. A. T. Hashem, D. E. Gbenga, A. I. Abubakar, A. M. Zeki *et al.*, "Progress on artificial neural networks for big data analytics: a survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 70 535–70 551, 2018.
- [3] G. Koppe, A. Meyer-Lindenberg, and D. Durstewitz, "Deep learning for small and big data in psychiatry," *Neuropsychopharmacology*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 176–190, 2021.
- [4] T. Nasser and R. Tariq, "Big data challenges," *J Comput Eng Inf Technol* 4: 3. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2324>, vol. 9307, no. 2, 2015.
- [5] A. K. Bhadani and D. Jothimani, "Big data: challenges, opportunities, and realities," *Effective big data management and opportunities for implementation*, pp. 1–24, 2016.
- [6] O. Russakovsky, J. Deng, H. Su, J. Krause, S. Satheesh, S. Ma, Z. Huang, A. Karpathy, A. Khosla, M. Bernstein *et al.*, "Imagenet large scale visual recognition challenge," *International journal of computer vision*, vol. 115, pp. 211–252, 2015.
- [7] R. Girshick, J. Donahue, T. Darrell, and J. Malik, "Rich feature hierarchies for accurate object detection and semantic segmentation," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2014, pp. 580–587.
- [8] A. Graves, A.-r. Mohamed, and G. Hinton, "Speech recognition with deep recurrent neural networks," in *2013 IEEE international conference on acoustics, speech and signal processing*. Ieee, 2013, pp. 6645–6649.
- [9] K. Simonyan and A. Zisserman, "Two-stream convolutional networks for action recognition in videos," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 27, 2014.
- [10] D. Hendrycks and K. Gimpel, "A baseline for detecting misclassified and out-of-distribution examples in neural networks," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2017.
- [11] Z. Hao, G. Xu, Y. Luo, H. Hu, J. An, and S. Mao, "Multi-agent collaborative inference via dnn decoupling: Intermediate feature compression and edge learning," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, 2022.
- [12] S. Sun, W. Chen, L. Wang, X. Liu, and T.-Y. Liu, "On the depth of deep neural networks: A theoretical view," *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. vol. 30, no. no. 1, 2016.
- [13] J. Kittler, M. Hatef, R. Duin, and J. Matas, "On combining classifiers," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 226–239, 1998.
- [14] Y. Liu, Y. Kang, C. Xing, T. Chen, and Q. Yang, "A secure federated transfer learning framework," *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 70–82, 2020.
- [15] H. Yong, J. Huang, X. Hua, and L. Zhang, "Gradient centralization: A new optimization technique for deep neural networks," in *Computer Vision–ECCV 2020: 16th European Conference, Glasgow, UK, August 23–28, 2020, Proceedings, Part I 16*. Springer, 2020, pp. 635–652.

- [16] S. Vekkot, D. Gupta, M. Zakariah, and Y. A. Alotaibi, "Emotional voice conversion using a hybrid framework with speaker-adaptive dnn and particle-swarm-optimized neural network," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 74 627–74 647, 2020.
- [17] Z. Wan, Z. Chang, Y. Xu, and B. Šavija, "Optimization of vascular structure of self-healing concrete using deep neural network (dnn)," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 364, p. 129955, 2023.
- [18] J. Park, P. Aryal, S. R. Mandumula, and R. P. Asolkar, "An optimized dnn model for real-time inferencing on an embedded device," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 8, p. 3992, 2023.
- [19] Z. Xiao, Q. Yan, and Y. Amit, "Likelihood regret: An out-of-distribution detection score for variational auto-encoder," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 33, pp. 20 685–20 696, 2020.
- [20] S. Sagiroglu and D. Sinanc, "Big data: A review," in *2013 international conference on collaboration technologies and systems (CTS)*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 42–47.
- [21] S. S. Shapiro and M. B. Wilk, "An analysis of variance test for normality (complete samples)," *Biometrika*, vol. 52, no. 3/4, pp. 591–611, 1965.
- [22] L. Deng, "The mnist database of handwritten digit images for machine learning research [best of the web]," *IEEE signal processing magazine*, vol. 29, no. 6, pp. 141–142, 2012.
- [23] H. Xiao, K. Rasul, and R. Vollgraf, "Fashion-mnist: a novel image dataset for benchmarking machine learning algorithms," 2017.
- [24] A. Krizhevsky, "Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images," 2009.
- [25] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and G. E. Hinton, "Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 25, 2012.